

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

Abduvaliyeva Shalola Sadriddin qizi

*English teacher for lawyers, Department
of General Education Sciences*

Abstract. Teaching is the process of attending to people's needs, experiences and feelings, and intervening so that they learn particular things, and go beyond the given. Teaching process is a duration that includes classroom management. If teachers want to teach effectively they should know how to manage the classroom in a perfect way. That's why this article explains some specific features about classroom management.

Key words: teaching process, classroom, classroom management.

Global object of any educational arrangement is alertness of adolescent bearing for able accord in all fields of action of a society. For accomplishment of this cold educational action should be beneath architecture in appearance of appearance of advance of a avant-garde poly-cultural association for which advantage of allied languages and cultures are characteristic, first, and secondly, advantage of texts and the argument formats circulating in all-around advice space, created by avant-garde agency of a accumulation communication.

Teachers after academic abecedary training tend to imitate administration techniques acclimated back they were in school. But autograph out amaranthine pages, or shouting, or abasement the apprentice are aloof not able nor acceptable. Respect for the adolescent is uppermost.

Teachers without formal teacher training tend to imitate management techniques used when they were in school. But writing out endless pages, or shouting, or humiliation the student are just not effective nor acceptable. Respect for the child is uppermost.

1. The teacher should remember that young children and the not so young - can concentrate only for short periods. The teacher should change activities every 20-25 minutes.

2. There are different students in class: passive receivers of information or active participants. The teacher should call on many children to answer or to ask questions. He/she should involve children have less time to “fool around” and bother others.

The subject matter should be relevant to the age level. The teacher can use visual aids in his/her teaching. Flashcards for practice with irregular verbs are appreciate by students of all ages.

The teacher shouldn't be always behind his/her desk or in front of the board. He/she should walk around when children are doing seat work.

He/she should encourage them; should spot check some assignments that the teacher has not been able to check.

If the teacher follows there points he/she is already on the right track. The teacher should remember to keep his/her voice at a normal level and should not shout to be heard. Most classes respond well when they realize they will have to stop talking in order to hear the teacher. If there is a noise in one comer of the room during the lesson, the teacher should stop and wait. The guilty parties will usually stop.

The teacher should realize too, that a classroom does not always have to be silent. There is “good” noise when children are working together, solving problems, and of course, talking in discussion groups.

The teacher should allow children to express themselves. If a child wants to share an event with the class and work is moving along smoothly, the teacher should take the time to listen. When words from the native tongue slip in during these exchanges, as they will, the teacher should have another child tell the class what the word means in English.

Effective classrooms are those in which orders are not always being given. At the beginning of the school term, the teacher should take 15 minutes and make the ground rules clear. Some of the most frequently used are:

- We always raise our hand and wait to be called on before speaking.
- We never interrupt a classmate while he or she is speaking.
- We always ask for permission before leaving the room.
- We remain seated while others are speaking
- We respect our classmates' property.
- The children will enjoy their English classes and will look forward to them.

Teachers should be guided in teaching by 2 fundamentals:

1. To turn to as good account as possible children's tremendous ability to memorize;
2. To combine activities such as looking at pictures and coloring them while sounding them;

Teachers ought to design their own lesson plans, keeping the instructions they think are appropriate, adopting the ones that can be adapted, ignoring what is not suitable, and even inserting their own activities and supplementary materials if need be. It is obvious that lesson planning is central to any teaching activity. This does not mean that the lesson plan should replace the textbook; both are necessary for effective teaching. However, unlike the textbook, the lesson plan is "ephemeral" in a positive sense. That is, it is subject to changes in the context that stands for the setting, the pupils, their learning styles, the time of the lesson, and the objectives of the course.

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